

VIEWS ON THE AVAILABILITY TEXTBOOKS AND COURSE MATERIALS

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Abstract. Harmer (2001) indicated that “Many good textbooks are attractively presented and they are prepared with a good structure that offers a coherent syllabus, satisfactory language control and motivating texts and tapes”. However, as a result of the expansion of digital resources (e.g., online databases, e-books, open educational resources), nowadays students often struggle to find reliable sources. The aim of this study is to examine students' opinions regarding the accessibility (e.g., physical availability, online access,) of textbooks and other course materials. By doing an online survey among 38 students, this research examined how students evaluate the availability of materials and their access to the available in libraries. The findings reveal that only 13.2% of students depend on library books frequently while the majority 47.4% use them sometimes. The data also indicates that numerous students do not use library resources. In order to improve students' experiences, the results highlight the necessity of increased accessibility and knowledge of library services. This study sample was limited to a smaller group of students; further research should be done to get a deeper understanding of students' patterns of using digital resources.

Keywords: textbook availability, course materials accessibility, library usage, e-books, digital resources, student perceptions, higher education, academic performance, open educational resources (OER), Uzbekistan, Kimyo International University in Tashkent, barriers to access, format compatibility, student engagement.

Introduction

While shares of print book readers and audiobook listeners remain mostly unchanged from a Center survey conducted in 2019, there has been an uptick in the share of Americans who report reading e-books, from 25% to 30%. Textbooks and course materials are crucial items in educational institutions that aid in student's academic growth and learning. Students who have possession of these instruments are better equipped to interact with their coursework, gain a deeper comprehension of the material, and improve their entire educational experiences. Despite that, many students continue to have serious concerns about the availability of textbooks and course materials, which affects their opportunities to successfully study. Students at Kimyo International University in Tashkent (KIUT) face a number of obstacles when it comes to obtaining course materials: some find it difficult to identify contemporary or course-specific resources or to retrieve physical documents from the university library due to existing restrictions. While digital materials offer an alternative, their usefulness and usability vary among students. Although the use of digital learning has been growing, little is known about how these obstacles with digital learning impact KIUT students. The purpose of this study is to investigate how students' academic performance is affected by the obstacles they encounter when trying to acquire course materials. Finding effective methods of guaranteeing fair distribution of educational materials primarily requires an

understanding of these problems. This article examines how easily KIUT students can acquire course materials, rely on various sources, handle obstacles when using printed or digital resources, and succeed in using university libraries.

Literature Review

Impact of accessibility on academic performance

In educational research, course materials accessibility has received significant attention, particularly in higher education institutions. Several research investigations demonstrate how the availability of resources affects students' motivation, grades, academic achievement and overall educational experiences. The University of the Pacific (2020) raises concerns about the objectivity, accuracy, timelines and authority of Open Educational Resources (OER). Questions are also raised about their long-term sustainability, particularly regarding how content creators can continue producing quality materials without reliable financial support. Despite these issues, some researchers view OER as a means of democratizing academic content, especially for students from low-income backgrounds burdened by the rising cost of textbooks (Jenkins et al., 2020; Stein et al., 2017). This study supports OER use within South Africa higher education, noting that its growth has been influenced not only by rising textbook prices but also by the expanding student population (Ndebele et al., 2022).

Digital tools and student diversity

According to Bond et al. (2018) university lecturers emphasize the importance of both technical and instructional support. From an administration perspective, many higher education institutions have embraced technology to provide flexible learning opportunities and timely mentoring, aiming to enhance the quality of education and streamline teaching processes. Depending on the supporting infrastructure, digital technologies present themselves in various forms. Learning platforms and digital tools have become essential in addressing the evolving needs and practices of modern education.

Various independent factors influence how students perceive quality, age, gender, level of study (undergraduate or graduate), race/ethnicity, academic discipline, motivation for learning and prior experience with online platforms.

Institutional barriers to access

Research by Iqbal et al. (2021) in Pakistan's higher education institutions revealed that students face challenges accessing digital resources due to restricted access, lack of user knowledge, unreliable information, and poor internet speeds. Although previous studies such as Iqbal et al. (2021) have identified important issues in Pakistan's higher education institutions such as poor internet connectivity, limited access to digital resources and lack of user knowledge. However, above mentioned research does not provide practical remedies to address these problems. The relationship between these digital barriers and how they affect student's performance is also not studied particularly in a variety of institutional demographic contexts in Uzbekistan

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore students' views on the availability of textbooks and course materials at Kimyo International University in Tashkent (KIUT). The sample consisted of 38 students of both genders, aged 18 to 23 years, recruited through convenience sampling. Data were collected using an online survey administered via Google Forms. The survey questions were adapted from the article "Affordable and Open Textbooks," ensuring a validated framework for investigating student perceptions of textbook

accessibility. The online format guaranteed participant anonymity, as no personally identifying information was collected. Ethical considerations included informed consent obtained through the survey preamble, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw without penalty.

The survey included closed-ended and open-ended items addressing library book usage, enjoyment of library services, challenges in accessing course materials, e-book experiences, and perceived impact on academic performance. Quantitative responses (e.g., Likert-scale and multiple-choice items) were tabulated and presented as percentages and frequencies, while qualitative responses were thematically categorized to identify recurring patterns. The findings were interpreted in relation to the research aim of understanding students' accessibility challenges and library usage patterns. This methodological approach provided a comprehensive understanding of how KIUT students experience and evaluate the availability of textbooks and course materials.

Results

It has been found that nearly 80 percent of the students reported using e-books.

Views on the availability of textbooks and course materials

Figure 1. Library book usage

The largest portion, 47.4%, indicated that they use library books sometimes suggesting occasional but not consistent use. Meanwhile, 26.3% of the respondents reported that they have never used library books, highlighting a significant portion of students who are disengaged from library books. In contrast, 13.2% use them regularly, and another 13.2% use them all the time, reflecting a smaller group of frequent users.

Figure 2. What you enjoy about library books

The most appreciated aspect is that students do not have to pay for library membership, noted by 18 respondents (47.4%). This highlights the value placed on free access to academic

resources. Additionally, 12 students (31.6%) indicated that they like not having to purchase the books, emphasizing the cost saving benefit of the library. Ease of use was another positive factor chosen by 9 students (23,7%), while 6 participants (15.8%) appreciated the availability of relevant materials in the library database. These results suggest that financial convenience and accessibility are among the key reasons students find library services.

Figure 3. Challenges in accessing course materials.

The majority, 50%, reported that they sometimes struggle to access their reading materials. Additionally, 21.1% of students mentioned they regularly face difficulties and 5.3% experience problems all the time. On the other hand, 23.7% of the participants claimed that they never have trouble accessing assigned readings, showing that for nearly a quarter of students, the system works effectively.

Figure 4. Exploring the Impact of E-Book Access on Student Grades and Retention.

Figure 4 illustrates that 47.4% think having access to ebooks improves their grades and retention, whereas 13.2% responded “no”. It’s interesting to note that 39.5% of students chose “I don’t know” to express uncertainty. This implies that a large percentage of students recognize the advantages, a sizable portion are either unclear or have not noticed obvious connections.

The most common issue indicated by 44.7% (17 respondents) was running out of battery while reading. This was followed by format compatibility problems with 34.2% (13 respondents) unable to open the ebook due to formatting issues. Additionally, 23.7% (9 respondents) experienced issues where the e-book did not load properly. Less frequent but still notable were technical difficulties with 10.5% (4 respondents) experiencing app crashes and 7.9% (3 respondents) reported that their screen froze during access attempts. Overall, the analysis shows that both technical limitations of devices and file compatibility issues significantly impact the user experience with e-books among participants.

Figure 5. Common Issues Encountered with E-Books Among Peers

Discussion

According to research conducted by Iqbal et al. (2021) in Pakistani higher education institutions, students encounter significant difficulties when utilizing digital resources. These challenges include limited access to digital materials, a lack of user proficiency, unreliable information, and slow internet speeds. Such barriers have been documented as major obstacles to effective learning in developing country contexts, where infrastructure and digital literacy often lag behind institutional expectations.

However, the present research indicates that students at Kimyo International University in Tashkent face different types of challenges while accessing e-books. Based on the survey results, the most commonly reported problem was device battery depletion during reading, followed by the inability to open e-books due to format incompatibility. Furthermore, a sizable portion of students experienced screen freezing, application crashes, and loading issues. These findings suggest that while Pakistani students struggle primarily with connectivity and access, KIUT students are more hindered by device limitations and technical compatibility problems. Consequently, the results highlight the need for strategies to encourage more consistent library usage among students, including better device support, standardized file formats, and improved technical infrastructure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research set out to explore availability of textbooks and course materials. The findings demonstrate that many students use library books occasionally, though some have never used them at all. A smaller group uses them all the time, suggesting varying levels of engagement with library resources. The main reason why students appreciate library services is the absence of membership fees, highlighting the importance of financial convenience. Other appreciated aspects include the ease of using library books and the availability of relevant materials through the library database. Many students still struggle to access the course materials. While some participants reported occasional challenges, others deal with problems on a daily basis. However, a smaller group had no trouble getting their readings, suggesting that some people benefit from the existing system. When it comes to e-books, students believe that they help improve academic performance. Some of them do not perceive any benefit, while significant numbers are unsure, there is a need for more consistent and effective experiences with digital resources.

The results emphasize the need for increased awareness, affordability and accessibility in order to effectively support student learning through library and digital services. iqbal

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